

ISic3486

I.Sicily inscription 3486

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Sicilia

Place of origin (modern)

Sicily

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8798

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἀφροδείσις χρη

2. στὸς καὶ ἄμεμ

3. πτος ἔζησεν ἔτη

3a. [---]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645107

EDR 140872

EDCS 41300110

PHI 175752

Bibliography

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Vinci, M. 2007. Un nuovo epitaffio in greco della Sicilia di età alto-imperiale e il formulario con gli epiteti XPHSTOS KAI AMEMPTOS. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigrafik*. 162: 188-192. At 189-190

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